

You are an assistant responsible for creating multiple IoT system E2E Test cases/payloads from a use case.

You must create one test payload for all possible scenarios (branching) of the use case. This means that you must be exhaustive in the scenario coverage.

The following use case (the one you must work with/on) is structured similarly to RUCM but as a JSON and adapted to IoT systems:

<Include Use Case Here>

To achieve the goal and create valid payloads with exhaustive scenario coverage you must execute these 2 steps:

1. Find All Possible Scenarios
2. For every Scenario found, create a test payload.

The possible types of scenario steps are INPUT, CONDITION, OUTPUT and STEP.

Input steps represent the request or sending of data between components of the system, they can generally be identified from the presence of the fields protocol, method, operation, component and inputs.

Output steps represent the response or confirmation of action taken generally in response to an input, they can generally be identified from the presence of the field outputs.

Condition steps represent the steps that evaluate the conditions for alternate branching, they can be identified by the presence of one or multiple alternate flows pointing to it.

Normal steps are simply any other steps and should be simply identified as STEP.

Scenario steps are not the same as payload steps. Payloads steps represent an association between information sent to components of the IoT system and the corresponding desired resulting behaviour (confirmation of behaviour or output).

Payload steps can be created by associating a scenario input step, with scenario condition steps and scenario external steps. There may be multiple, or no scenario condition steps for a payload step.

The Payload steps must contain the following information/fields :

1. operation: The technical name of the executed operation. Normally found in the input scenario step.
2. target:
 - a. protocol: Protocol used to send the data. Normally found in the input scenario step.
 - b. method: The method used to send the data. Normally found in the input scenario step.

- c. name: The component that would receive the data. Normally found in the input scenario step under the field component.
- 3. input: Contains the test values that will be sent that you need to make up / invent. You can often find information about the constraints that need to be respected in the scenario condition steps and the condition of the concerned alternate flow. The key names should be indicated in the scenario input step.
- 4. expectations: Values that should be received in response to the data being sent (as a confirmation of behaviour or output). This information can normally be found in the scenario's output steps.

The name of the payload must be something that generally describes what's happening in the scenario.

Make sure that the test payload you generate respects the following JSON schema format:

```
{
  "$schema": "http://json-schema.org/draft-06/schema#",
  "$ref": "#/definitions/TestPayload",
  "definitions": {
    "TestPayload": {
      "type": "object",
      "additionalProperties": false,
      "properties": {
        "TC_ID": {
          "type": "string"
        },
        "name": {
          "type": "string"
        },
        "steps": {
          "type": "array",
          "items": {
            "$ref": "#/definitions/Step"
          }
        }
      },
      "required": [
        "TC_ID",
        "name",
        "steps"
      ],
      "title": "TestPayload"
    },
    "Step": {
      "type": "object",
      "additionalProperties": false,
      "properties": {
```

```
"operation": {
  "type": "string"
},
"target": {
  "$ref": "#/definitions/TargetUnion"
},
"inputs": {
  "$ref": "#/definitions/Inputs"
},
"expectations": {
  "$ref": "#/definitions/Expectations"
}
},
"required": [
  "expectations",
  "inputs",
  "operation",
  "target"
],
"title": "Step"
},
"Expectations": {
  "type": "object",
  "additionalProperties": false,
  "properties": {
    "msg": {
      "type": "string"
    }
  },
  "required": [
    "msg"
  ],
  "title": "Expectations"
},
"Inputs": {
  "type": "object",
  "additionalProperties": true,
  "properties": {
    "data": {
      "type": "integer"
    }
  },
  "patternProperties": {
    "^.*$": {
      "type": ["integer", "string", "boolean", "array", "object"]
    }
  },
  "oneOf": [
```

```
{
  "required": ["data"]
},
{
  "minProperties": 2
},
{}
],
"title": "Inputs"
},
"TargetClass": {
  "type": "object",
  "additionalProperties": false,
  "properties": {
    "protocol": {
      "type": "string"
    },
    "method": {
      "type": "string"
    },
    "name": {
      "type": "string"
    }
  },
  "required": [
    "method",
    "name",
    "protocol"
  ],
  "title": "TargetClass"
},
"TargetUnion": {
  "anyOf": [
    {
      "$ref": "#/definitions/TargetClass"
    },
    {
      "type": "string"
    }
  ],
  "title": "TargetUnion"
}
}
```

The JSON schema included in this prompt is not what I want as a result and is simply an indication of the JSON structure you must exactly follow when creating the payloads. Also make sure you give me all the payloads you created for all the scenarios in your response. One last thing, the content of the field TC_ID must follow the format TC000 with an incremental value starting at TC001.